

An Assessment of the Nursi's Perspective on the Role of Faith in Building a Socio-Economic Balance in the Twenty-First Century

*Professor Vaffi Foday Sheriff¹, Dr Adam Yusuf Adam²

¹ Department of Islamic Studies, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria.

² Department of *Shari'ah* Studies, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria.

*Corresponding author: [Professor Vaffi Foday Sheriff](#)

Department of Islamic Studies, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria.

Abstract

The twenty-first century has no doubt been the most complex and challenging epoch in the socioeconomic history of human existence on earth due to many reasons. Islam, as a religion and way of life, has promulgated principles on how best social and economic systems effectively work to ensure human prosperity. The root of that principle is belief, which serves as an instrument that provides man with absolute social security and balance. To perfectly express this fact, Bediuzzaman Said Nursi, in the *Risale-i Nur*, has explored the human socio-economic system as it relates to belief in the existence of Allah, life and the universe. This paper, therefore, questions the concept of belief from Nursi's perspective, examines its essence, and its role(s) in building socio-economic balance in the 21st century and beyond. However, the analytical method used in writing this paper discovers that Nursi is not only a religious teacher but also a modern social analyst. *Risale* has explicitly exposed that belief is the foundation of the socio-economic balance of human societies that must be based on firm knowledge of Allah, certainty in the occurrence of resurrection, divine determining that allows man's free choice and expertise to design the socio-economic system would work for every stratum of the society. These, according to Nursi, guarantee the pleasure of this life and salvation in the next.

Keywords: Faith (*Iman*), Socio-economic, Balance, Sa'id Nursi, *Risale-i-Nur*.

Introduction

In the Name of Allah, Most Gracious, Most Merciful

There is a greater concern among people about the socioeconomic problems affecting the world today. The approaches used in finding the roots of such problems differ as to the backgrounds and worldviews of those attempting to identify them. Yet, the popular secular view sees scarcity as the root cause of environmental issues, inequality, inflation, irrational behaviour, unemployment, and recession, both at the micro and macro levels of the globe. To some, the flaws and inconsistencies in the socioeconomic theory and practices of modern man, built upon the basics that contradict the Islamic tenets are the reasons behind the emergence of the socio-economic catastrophes of modern times.

Islam is a complete way of life that has established a framework for our socio-religious, political, and economic aspects of human life. In the socio-economic aspect, it commands compassion and discourages self-centeredness. It states that one is free to trade and make wealth as much as he likes but society has also its rights. This right of society is legislated by Allah (SWT) in various legal injunctions dealing with personal and interpersonal interactions within a given society. Thus, the basis on which this Islamic religious philosophy can effectively work stems from one's conviction and submissiveness to Allah's existence and sublimity of His legislation, that is faith, otherwise known as *Iman*.

It is based on this that this paper examines the concept of socio-economic principles and their importance in human social settings. It studies Nursi's socio-economic theory as it affects one's belief and practices in his function as a servant

and Allah's trustee on the surface of this earth. It explores Nursi's approach to the role of belief in building socio-economic balances in human society and the extent to which the approach is distinct from that of modern thinkers. It shows how Nursi's allegorical explanations of the ethos of faith can help in mitigating or reducing the socio-economic imbalance affecting the social order of the 21st human century, and how that can be sustained. It concludes by emphasizing the veracity of Nursi's approach and the principles he outlined in not only providing socio-economic balance but also maintaining social security that ensures human pleasure on the earth and salvation in the hereafter.

Overview of the Concept and Contemporary Socio-Economic Problems

Social economics is a branch of economics and social science that focuses on the relationship between social behaviour and economics. Thus, socio-economic rights are ultimately designed to provide certain entitlements for the interests of individuals in having access to certain socio-economic resources.ⁱ Social economics consists of two broad perspectives. The first involves the application of the basic theoretical tools of neoclassical microeconomics to areas of human behaviour not traditionally considered part of economics proper, such as crime and punishment, drug abuse, marriage, and family decisions. The second consists of applying the ideas of social sciences, such as sociology, psychology, and identity group studies to subjects of an economic nature such as consumer behaviour or labour markets. These practitioners of social economics use history, current events, politics, and other social sciences to predict social trends that could potentially impact the economy.ⁱⁱ Generally, one can say, social economics is primarily concerned with the interplay between social processes and economic activity within a given society. Hence, it attempts to explain how a particular social group or socio-economic class behaves within a society, including their actions as consumers. Socio-economics is sometimes used as an umbrella term for various areas of inquiry. The term social economics may refer broadly to the use of economics in the study of society. More narrowly, contemporary practice considers behavioural interactions of individuals and groups through social capital and social markets and the formation of social norms.

Consequently, socioeconomic development is the process of social and economic development of a society. Socio-economic development is measured with indicators, such as the growth of domestic products, life expectancy, literacy and levels of employment. Changes in less-tangible factors are also considered, such as personal dignity, freedom of association, personal safety, freedom from fear of physical harm, and the extent of participation in civil society. Based on this, the socio-economic scenario of the world today indicates that there have been socio-economic problems affecting various aspects of human life. This has been compounded by the recent Covid-19 pandemic that led to the term 'synchronized slowdown' being used to describe global economic growth as a factor that creates a stagnation of an average income level, called the 'middle-income-trap' or financial volatility of an individual.ⁱⁱⁱ This economic predicament turned to breed problems that are personal, structural and fundamental in the socio-economic life of the world. Thus, the theories of social-economic diverge from conventional economic theories. The theories of social economics often consider factors that are outside the focus of mainstream economics, including the effect of culture, environment and religion on consumption and creation of wealth this paper harps on the religious effect, and in particular, Islamic religious faith and its role in building socio-economic balance.

Theoretical Framework on the Essence of Faith (Iman) and its Social Role in Islam

Generally, faith in Islam denotes *Iman*, which means to believe with one's heart, to confess with one's tongue and to demonstrate in one's physical actions. Thus, *Iman* is the soul of hearts and bodies. It is the key to happiness as it is a means of salvation in this life and the next. It brings contentment and satisfaction to the heart.^{iv} Moreover, *Iman* has six pillars that every Muslim has to believe in them, accept wholeheartedly, and be fully convinced with them. These six pillars are, to believe in: Allah (SAW), His Angels; His Messengers; His Books; The Last Day (Day of Resurrection and Judgement); and Fate and Destiny; whether it seems good or bad. Belief in Allah entails that Allah is One. He is Self-Sufficient. He does not give birth, nor was He borne, and there is nothing like Him. Belief in His Angels means that Angels are creatures of Allah, whom He created to serve Him, and they fail not to obey His commands, and they are prompt as they are commanded. Belief in His Scriptures refers to those scriptures that contained His commandments to those who came before us, and the one to serve as our life manual. The Qur'an in our hands today serves as an example and is the most authentic scripture of Allah. It is going to be in use till the Day of Judgement. Belief in His Messengers as the chosen from among humans to communicate with Allah through Angels and revelations and to then convey the message(s) of Allah to His servants, to remind them of their ultimate purpose in this existence, and to guide them towards the pleasure of Allah. The next is belief in the Last Day, which is the Day of Resurrection. The Last Day is when everything is going to be eternal. There will be two destinations when the last day occurs. Heaven will be for those who chose righteousness in this life, and Hellfire will be for those who chose infidelity and transgression. Finally, belief in Fate and Destiny whether they are good or bad. This entails that the world is meant to be the home for all trials and tests. That is why not all incidents are logical to human understanding. We have the right to choose, but at the same time, we are obliged to believe in Fate and Destiny.^v Thus, the fact about *Iman* in Islam is based on three components, if any of it is missing, the *Iman* may not be valid and may not be considered a genuine one. These three components are: to believe with the heart; to confess with the tongue; and to demonstrate in physical action. The second and third components are

true reflections of what the heart is carrying. In other words, the heart is a common ground for what the tongue expresses and what the body physically demonstrates.^{vi}

Faith (*Iman*) therefore, is a conviction that there is no god but Allah. This seemingly carries the greatest meaning in the whole of Islam. It is a general view of the reality of truth and the world, of space and time, of history and destiny based on the principles that Allah and non-Allah; are the Creator and creature. The first one is Allah (SWT). He alone is Allah, the eternal, the Creator, and the Transcendent. Nothing is like unto Him. The second, is the order of space and time, of experience of creation, which includes all creatures, humans, things, plants, paradise and hell and they are becoming into being.^{vii} The realization of this order is ideational, which gives reasons to man to understand the reality of things through thinking, reasoning, intuition and apprehension. In the end, man understands that the world has not been created in vain or in a spot. It is created in perfect order and for a purpose. And since everything was created for a purpose, the realization of that purpose must be possible in space and time through the process of *Takhlif* (charge, moral obligation, and responsibility). Thus, that is the absolute reality and the divine wisdom to be realized in the existence of Allah, His creation of things and the Day of Judgment.^{viii}

Man, therefore, must be capable of changing himself, his fellow human beings, or society, to actualize the divine pattern or command of Allah in him as well as in theirs. For, obeying Allah through His commandments is the key to incurring *falah* (success, development, and transformation), and to disobey Him is to incur punishment, suffering, unhappiness and agonies of failure.^{ix}

Nursi's Perspective of Faith (*Iman*) and Socio-Economic Balance in the 21st Century

Bediuzzaman Said Nursi (1876-1960), was a modern thinker and a religious teacher whose religious educational background shaped his worldview and ideas on the meaning of belief, life and the universe.^x To perfectly express his thought, Nursi demonstrated in action and his *magnum opus*, the *Risale-i-Nur*, that the core objective of the religion of Islam is the affirmation of the truth of the Qur'an, and protecting and strengthening one's faith (*Iman*) from not only the watershed of modernity but also naturalistic science and philosophy.^{xi} Thus, To portray this, Nursi's ideas of the role of faith in ensuring socio-economic balance and mitigating inequalities hinged on the following strategies:

a. Faith (*Iman*)

Faith, according to Nursi does not start and end with the declaration of the *Kalimah*, rather, it is the journey for strengthening faith and deriving knowledge. It is this kind of faith that guides human beings to the path of knowledge by inspiring them to learn about the universe as a book of wisdom that can be achieved perfectly through good deeds which is the duty to be realized by a true believer. Abandoning belief is tantamount to unbelief, which leads to meaningless and materialistic life.^{xii} It is between these two strings of realities that lie and evolve equitable, peaceful, comfortable and problem-free socio-economic life and *vice versa*.

b. Knowledge of Allah (*Iman-i-Tahkiki*)

The first principle required by an individual or a community in ensuring social and economic stability is 'knowledge', which according to Nursi signifies having a verified belief "*iman-i-Tahkiki*". This, according to him indicates the need for certain knowledge of all questions related to belief through close investigation, and to live unwaveringly per that which the belief has affirmed.^{xiii} He adds that true and pain-free pleasure is founded only in belief in Allah that illuminates the one professing it like a lighthouse, that even if his other human attributes waned and faded it will continue in existence and manifest so long as he/she continued to renew evidence as a firmer of belief.^{xiv} Nursi sees this foundational base of belief the seed that fruits of pleasures, and likened it with a *Tuba Tree* of paradise, while 'unbelief' is like the *Zakkum-Tree* of hell. Based on this, he concludes that a balance and security in the human social and economic life can only be found in Islam and belief, on which he advises that we should continually say: "Praise be to Allah for the religion of Islam and perfect belief".^{xv}

c. Human Responsibility and Accountability (*Al-Amanah*)

Nursi holds the view that belief consists of two parts. First, comprising a concise explanation of one comprehensive result of the numerous spiritual benefits of belief in resurrection and its vital consequences, and second, a demonstration of how essential it is for human life, especially in the socio-economic balance of a society in which he lives. Though, Nursi shows that modern sociologists, politicians and moralists, who govern mankind were unable to understand that, hence connecting the dots that exist between the belief in resurrection and its significance on the socio-economic life of a society. He cautions that the sooner the realization of the truth of the resurrection and its recurrences, the better for humanity to realize its essence and its universal need, and clearer the path for the creation of socio-economic balance for the existence as a man and Allah's vicegerent would become. This accordingly, tells that it is Allah, and only through Him that our existence could be illumined with the light of belief and moonlike luminosity of the Qur'an, to make the awe and terror of our life transformed into tranquillity and joy. Thus, he inferred that "*after Divine unity, everything he (man) claimed throughout his life was centred on the resurrection of the dead*".^{xvi}

On this, Nursi believes that the affirmation of the principle of belief in resurrection instils in man the wisdom of being accountable in all his actions. The appearance of socio-economic inequities in the world's arena today would keep reminding him of the calamity of suffering, perhaps ten times greater than the actual calamity he suffers from the injustice he is engulfed with. Thus, he may adjust to hold on to the tenets of belief which are explicitly communicated by the Qur'an and the reality of life. This self-social redress is seen by Nursi as the best thing man can do to create the desired socio-economic balance required for human social existence in the twenty-first century.^{xvii}

d. Socio-Economic Compliance and *Shari'ah*

The phrase "and in His scripture" in the chain of the Islamic belief system, signifies the testimonies to the truth of the revealed scriptures in general and in Qur'an and the *Shari'ah* of the Prophet Muhammad (SAW) in particular.^{xviii} The All-Wise Qur'an according to Nursi is a most elevated expounder, a most eloquent translator of the almighty Qur'an of the universe. It is the criterion which instructs man concerning his social and economic welfare on the leaves of time.^{xix} Thus, he believes that the human socio-economic balance is so much connected to the light of belief and the *Shari'ah* of the Qur'an that would remove the inequalities, deprivation and poverty man is experiencing in life and be transformed into quietude and pleasure. Nursi then advises that to make that into reality, human beings must embark on the ship of the truth of Islam, and fashion their lives in the dockyard of the wisest Qur'an. By doing so, he assures that the modern man will surely pass the socio-economic inequities that he is experiencing in various aspects of life, and the alternation of life, which is boarded by unnumbered corpses, borne on the waves of the years and centuries, can be cast into nothingness.^{xx} Nursi, therefore is unwavering that the principles and matters of *Shari'ah* are the most beneficial remedies for multifaceted human socio-economic unevenness, from the sickness of the spirit, disturbances of the mind, and turbulence of the heart that are manifest in the socio-economic imbalance. Thus, he confirmed that the argument that is being put forward by social and economic philosophers cannot take place of that which the Qur'an has already laid down, and to some extent, he has made it clear in the *Risale-i-Nur* what he had personally experienced on that.^{xxi} On that note, Nursi concludes that the *Shari'ah* of Islam is the decisive statement of the Qur'an and irrefutable and decisive proof that cannot be doubted, in the sense that the expositions of the Qur'an on what could make our socio-economic life better cannot be substituted nor downgraded with that of man's partial knowledge, or a system created by the knowledge of someone unlettered, that is the unbeliever.^{xxii}

e. Positive Action

It is of human perplexity that Nursi sees the connection between human socio-economic balance and its inequities in the light of the belief in Divine Determining. This is based on the fact that life is the most comprehensive mirror of the Creator of the universe and the most perfect sample and index of dominical activity. It is a programme through which the mysteries of life necessitate the creatures to be predisposed to conform to order and regularity, to be observed in specific individual existence and the creative commands in their collective life.^{xxiii} He clarifies that a valuable aspect of man's socio-economic life is constricted by Divine power and determining, so much so that, if a man uses those immaterial desires of his soul for the minor pleasures of this worldly life, he will decay and decompose in the midst of difficulties of this life. If, however, he nurtures his abilities with the water of Islam and light of belief under the service and servitude to Allah and uses his mental faculties through their true aims, that will be a seed of great value and a shining machine containing everlasting and permanent truth which will be the means of innumerable perfection and luminous fruits of the tree of the universe, and the blessed bounties in Paradise.^{xxiv}

Nursi indicts the notion which says: 'the creation of evil is evil, and the creation of bad is bad' and qualifies it as total misguidance and wrongful interpretation of the pillar of 'belief in Divine Determining, particularly in the socio-economic context. For, Nursi, both the good that is the balance, and the evil, that is, the inequities are from Allah. The above truth according to Nursi is explained and proved by the Qur'an insistence and repetition of the truth that evil provokes people in respect of destruction they commit to themselves or others, that those who believe, are in need of many cautions and great care in the face of those repeated warnings. It is for this reason that Allah, the Almighty, stretches out thousands of hands of compassion to people of belief in respect of those warnings. This individual and collective adjustment can give rise to social and economic balance in every society where man's evil actions have had it difficult for himself or others.^{xxv}

It is not out of sight from the various metaphorical examples of the *Risale-i-Nur*, for one to see the extent to which Nursi described the socio-economic order of human society as created by the All-Wise Maker that is Allah. In one particular place, Nursi is attracted to proclaim that:

Frugality and contentment are in conformity with the Divine wisdom; they treat the sense of taste as a doorkeeper and give it its remuneration accordingly. As for wastefulness, since it is to act contrary to wisdom, it swiftly receives its punishment, upsets the stomach, and causes real appetite to be lost. Producing from the

unnecessary variety of foods a false and artificial appetite causes indigestion and illness.^{xxvi}

Nursi's thoughts on belief advanced that of the modern thinkers in the theological realm, as he does not reject the power of human limitlessness in charting out his pleasure and salvation. This, in the sense that he does not dismiss the power that allows man to live in accordance with the advancement of his time, and if 'socio-economic balance' can be part of that meaning, as echoed in modern science and philosophy, then so be it. But, the veracity of that meaning or otherwise is dependent on its conformity with the tenets of belief and its implications in one's religious life. On this Nursi says:

A state of mind pleasing to the mature and perfected with their appreciation of meaning does not gratify the childish, whimsical and dissolute. It does not entertain them. In consequence, those raised amid base, dissolute, carnal and lusty pleasures will not experience a spiritual pleasure.

To explain the above, Nursi shows that Islamic socio-economic life is based on clear evidence and balance that is not restricted to an individual to prove to himself, but it is based on the conscience of innumerable matters that are common in the hearts. Hence, according to Nursi, Islam is based on two firm foundations; a) revelation and b) innate disposition, and these two have worked so effectively for so many centuries. He, therefore, calls that conscience can be used to work in providing and maintaining socio-economic balance, but that should be firmly rooted with principles that cannot be associated with irreligiosity. For this, he argues that the essentials of religion and the incontestable matters of Shari'ah are present in the heart to made human beings consciously reminded about this reality, so that they could always allow to apply them in their day-to-day menials to realize perfect balance and regular sequence that conformed with the principles of the innate nature of things and unity, so that the balance can be preserved and sustained, not only in the socio-economics but in other aspects of their lives.

Conclusion

Man, by virtue of his wants and needs, is idiosyncratic, but his desires as an individual entity are not separated from that of his society and its welfare. This unity of essence is cemented in Islam with the belief system that defines the purpose of life of the human species on the earth. At the centre of it, all is the social and economic life, where human knowledge can insert its effective power to realize its connection with the Creator on one hand and with other creatures on the other hand. Bediuzzaman Said Nursi, one of the 20th-century Muslim thinkers, has devoted his entire life to exhibiting the truth of Islam and proving the sublimity of the Qur'an and its *Shari'ah*. He opined that the Islamic belief system is a machine-like engine that guides man's inner and practical conviction to the recognition of the pleasure of this life that guarantees one's salvation in the hereafter. The modern conception of pleasure made socio-economic life incomprehensible not only to social scientists but also philosophers who always outlined principles that are yet to guarantee such social and economic balance or its security. But, Nursi, from the light of the All-Wise Qur'an, underscores that firm belief, knowledge of Allah, *al-Amanah*, holding on to the principles of the Qur'an, resurrection and divine determining are not only articles of faith (*Iman*), but the basis of realization and harnessing socio-economic balance for human prosperity on earth and its sustainability through human positive actions.

Works Cited

- ⁱ David, Bilchitz, "Socio-Economic Rights, Economic Crisis and Legal Doctrine", in *I.con*, volume, 12 (2014), 713.
- ⁱⁱ Theo, Suranyi-Unger, *Economics in the Twentieth Century: The History of it International Development*, (London: Routledge, 2003), 22- 32.
- ⁱⁱⁱ Jose Antonio Ocampo, "Uncertainty Surrounding the Global economy and the Implication on the Global Development Agenda" in United Nations, *Economic and Social of Challenges and Opportunities*, (New York, 2020), 14-21.
- ^{iv} Rohi, Ba'albaki, *Al-Mawrid: A Modern Arabic-English Dictionary*, (Beirut: Dar al-Ilm lil Malāyin, 1995), 215.
- ^v Abu Hanifa, *Figh al-Akbar*, Hamid Algar (trans.), in *Journal of Al-Bayan* (1980), 1- 17.
- ^{vi} Yedullah, Kazmi, "Article of Faith and Organized Religion in Islam: Historicity and faith and Its Implication", in *Islamic Studies*, volume. 74, No. 2 (2008), 173 – 193.
- ^{vii} Josheph Kenny, *Christian-Islamic Preambles of Faith: An Exercise in the Philosophy of Religion or Kalam for our day Modeled after Thomas Aquinas*, (Washington DC: The Council for Research in Values and Philosophy, 1999), 49-53.
- ^{viii} Yadullah, Kazmi, "Faith and Knowledge in Islam: An Essay in Philosophy of Religion", in *Islamic Studies*, volume. 38, No. 4 (1999), 503 – 534.
- ^{ix} Isma'il Raji, *Al-Faruqi, Al-Tawhid: Its Implications for Thought and life*, (Herndon: The International Institute for Islamic Thought, 2000), 9- 13.
- ^x Sukran, vahide, "The Life and Times of Bediuzzaman Said Nursi", in *The Muslim World*, vol.89, Nos: 3-4, (1999), 208 – 244.

-
- ^{xi} Imtiyaz, Yusuf, “Bediuzzaman Said Nursi’s Discourse on Belief in Allah: A Study of Texts from ‘Risale-i-Nur’ Collection”, in Muslim World, volume, 89, No. 3-4 (1999), 342.
- ^{xii} Vaffi Foday, Sheriff, “Faith as the Foundation of Human Progress: Nursi’s Perspective”, in Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Science, volume. 4, Issue 8 (2018), 74.
- ^{xiii} Bediuzzaman Said Nursi, Staff of Moses, The Fruits of Belief, (Istanbul: Sozler Nesriyat, 2000), 26.
- ^{xiv} Bediuzzaman Said Nursi, Ishârât al-I’jâz fi Mazânn al-îjâz, Sukrah Vahide (trans.), (Istanbul: Sozler Nesriyat, 2007), 49.
- ^{xv} Bediuzzaman Said Nursi, The Flashes, the Thirtieth Flash, (Istanbul: Sozler Nesriyat, 2003), 448.
- ^{xvi} Said Nursi, The Staff of Moses..., 214.
- ^{xvii} Bediuzzaman Said Nursi, The Rays Collection, Sukran Vahide (trans.), (Istanbul: Sozler Nasriyet, 2000), 100.
- ^{xviii} Said Nursi, The Staff of Moses..., 215.
- ^{xix} Said Nursi, The Words..., The Twelfth word..., 215.
- ^{xx} Said Nursi, The Flashes..., the First Flash..., 20.
- ^{xxi} Bediuzzaman Said Nursi, The Words: on the Nature and Purpose of Man, Life and all Things, (The Twenty-Fifth word), Sukrah Vahide (trans), 449.
- ^{xxii} Said Nursi, The Words..., 154.
- ^{xxiii} Said Nursi, The Words..., The Tenth Word, Second part of an Addendum..., 123.
- ^{xxiv} Bediuzzaman Said Nursi, Letters: 1928 -1932, Sukran Vahide (trans.) ..., 770.
- ^{xxv} Said Nusri, The Flashes, The Thirteenth Flash..., 111 -112.
- ^{xxvi} Said Nursi, The Flashes..., (The Nineteenth Flash) ..., 191.